

regeneration medium with 1 mg kinetin/liter and 1 mg naphthalene acetic acid/liter and 20 mg abscisic acid (ABA)/liter for 4 wk and then to ABA-free semisolid MS regeneration medium.

Results (Table 1) showed that at 20 krad, glucose addition increased callus production efficiency. Irradiation at 20 krad resulted in genetic alterations in the irradiated seeds such that adding glucose is necessary to induce high percentage of callus production. Such an improved efficiency may have been brought about by an increased requirement for glucose uptake and metabolism and by a change in the requirement of other cells for osmoticum.

Studies on plant regeneration showed that percentage of calli producing albino plants and average albino plant production were higher in E10 compared to G4, but the reverse was true in green plant regeneration

Table 1. Effect of glucose on irradiated Basmati 370 plants.

Media ^a	Irradiation dosage (krad)	Anthers plated (no.)	Calli produced (no.)	Callus production (%)
E10	0	1910	221	11.6
	20	694	220	31.7
G4	0	506	77	15.2
	20	708	52	7.3

^aE10 = with 5 g glucose/liter, G4 = without glucose.

Table 2. Effect of glucose on plant regeneration of irradiated Basmati 370.

Media ^a	Irradiation dosage (krad)	Total calli plated (no.)	Calli with green plants (%)	Av green plant production	Calli with albino plants (%)	Av albino plant production
E10	0	60	0	0	15.00	4.6
	20	84	1.2	5	34.52	1.79
G4	0	10	0	0	10.00	2
	20	23	26.1	5.2	8.7	1

^aE10 = with 5 g glucose/liter, G4 = without glucose.

(Table 2). This indicates that although glucose enhances callus production and

albinism, it diminishes green plant regeneration. *ℓ*

Effect of pollen development stage on callus induction and its relation to auricle distance in two rice varieties

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Callus production from uninucleate and binucleate pollen of japonica varieties Taipei 309 and Kulu was evaluated. Nuclear stages of pollen from panicles with auricle distances varying between 4.5 and 12.5 cm were scored before plating. A cold shock of 8°C for 8 d was given. Two liquid media, G4 and E10, were used. G4 contained B5 salts, vitamins, 20 g sucrose, 1 mg 2,4-D and 0.5 mg each of BAP and IAA/liter. E10 had an additional 5 g glucose/liter. Calli induced were scored 90 d after plating.

As overlapping of nuclear developmental stages was common (in the same spikelet, different pollen nuclei showed combinations of early and mid-uninucleate, mid- and late uninucleate, late uninucleate and early binucleate, etc.), the stage of each half of the panicle used for inoculation was fixed on the basis of the nuclear stage found in the

Stages of pollen development: A. mid-uninucleate, B. late uninucleate, C. early binucleate, D. mid-binucleate.

majority (75%) of the pollen stained. Plating of spikelets which had both uninucleate and binucleate pollen was avoided. Early uninucleate and late binucleate stages were discarded and only panicles with either mid- to late uninucleate or early to mid-binucleate pollen (see figure) were used for inoculation.

The nuclear stage of the pollen could be approximated to some extent by external features of the spikelet, but

such visual scoring was often erroneous. Microscopic scoring was done to determine pollen stage. Uninucleate stage anthers of both varieties induced a very high number of calli; those in the binucleate stage showed less (see table). Taipei 309 responded better to E10, while Kulu was better in G4.

Auricle distances of panicles could not be correlated with stage of pollen nuclear development and callus production efficiency. In both varieties,

Relation between auricle distance, nuclear stage,^a and callus induction in anther culture of Taipei 309 and Kulu. IRRI, 1986.

Taipei 309

Auricle distance (cm)	5.0		6.5		7.0		7.5		8.0		8.5		9.0		12.5	
	UN	BN	UN	BN	UN	BN	UN	BN	UN	BN	UN	BN	UN	BN	UN	BN
Stage of pollen	UN	BN	UN	BN	UN	BN	UN	BN	UN	BN	UN	BN	UN	BN	UN	BN
Anthers plated (no.)	125	50	75	175	125	75	200	175	500	200	175	125	475	200	-	100
Calli induced (no.)	807	503	117	410	2278	538	1825	1021	3168	204	809	249	3951	447	-	373

Kulu

Auricle distance (cm)	4.5		1.5		8.0		8.25		8.5		9.0		9.5		11.5	
	UN	BN	UN	BN	UN	BN	UN	BN	UN	BN	UN	BN	UN	BN	UN	BN
Stage of pollen	UN	BN	UN	BN	UN	BN	UN	BN	UN	BN	UN	BN	UN	BN	UN	BN
Anthers plated (no.)	175	-	125	-	225	-	100	150	125	-	150	550	400	175	375	250
Calli induced (no.)	42	-	196	-	1923	-	0	916	1877	-	350	250	1016	0	1905	345

UN = uninucleate, BN = binucleate.

panicles of varying auricle distances had both uninucleate and binucleate pollen (see table). In Taipei 309, panicles with 12.5 cm auricle distances were as efficient as those with 8.5 cm distance; in Kulu, panicles with 11.5 and 8.25 cm auricle distances were equal in total callus production. The most efficient

auricle distances for callus induction were 7.0 cm in Taipei 309 and 8.5 in Kulu.

The very high callus induction frequency recorded may be due to the long induction period (90 d) and the use of a liquid medium for callus induction. A liquid medium allows for fast

dispersal of calli away from the anther, leading to the production of more and more calli by lessening overcrowding within the responding anther. The calli can also undergo fragmentation in the medium, causing an apparent increase in the efficiency of callus induction. *ℵ*

Plant regeneration and screening from long-term NaCl-stressed rice callus

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Salinity is one of the major causes of reduced productivity in rice growing areas. Tissue culture could complement breeding techniques to produce variants which are tolerant of salt. The objectives of our study were to regenerate rice plants from long-term NaCl-stressed callus of variety Reiho and to determine if there is a direct relationship between

The response of calli of variety Reiho in different concentrations of NaCl.

Treatment (g NaCl/liter)	Initial weight ^a (g)	Final weight (g)	Relative increase in weight ^b (%)
0	0.0498	0.6882	1281.93
5	0.0513	0.6446	1156.53
10	0.0512	0.4551	788.87
15	0.0497	0.2762	455.73
20	0.0521	0.1607	208.44

^aAverage of 10 calli.

^b $\frac{\text{Final weight} - \text{initial weight}}{\text{Initial weight}} \times 100.$

tolerance for salt at the cellular level and at the plant level.

Dehulled mature seeds of variety Reiho were surface-sterilized with 70% ethyl alcohol followed by 0.1% mercuric chloride, then washed 4 times with sterile distilled water. The seeds were inoculated on Murashige and Skoog's medium (MSYC) with 2 mg 2,4-D/liter, 2 g casein hydrolysate/liter, 2 g yeast extract/liter, 30 g sucrose/liter and 8 g agar/liter at pH 5.8. The induced calli were allowed to proliferate for 4 wk (1 passage).

The proliferated calli were inoculated on selection medium (MSYC with 15 g NaCl/liter) and transferred to fresh medium every 4 wk. The cultures were kept in darkness with temperature maintained at 26-27 °C. After 32 passages, calli were transferred to Linsmaier and Skoog's regeneration medium with 1 mg benzylaminopurine/liter, 0.5 mg *a*-naphthaleneacetic acid/liter, 40 g sucrose/liter, and 8 g agar/liter at pH 5.8. The cultures were kept under continuous light (3 klx) at 26-27°C.

Eighteen individual calli stressed with

NaCl were transferred to regeneration medium and only 30% produced plants totalling 35. The regenerated plants were grown in Yoshida's culture solution for 30 d and then transferred to the same solution with different concentrations of NaCl: 0, 5, 10, and 15 g liter.

Although the calli tolerated exposure to 1.5% NaCl for 32 passages (32 mo), the regenerated plants did not survive when grown in culture solution containing 5, 10, and 15 g NaCl liter. Plants kept on control (no NaCl) flowered, but showed 100% sterility. The regenerated plants did not carry the NaCl tolerance trait present in the calli.

The regenerated plants exposed to different concentrations of NaCl showed an inverse relationship between the number of days of survival and NaCl concentration in the culture solution.

Similarly, calli that have been cultured in NaCl-enriched medium (15 g NaCl/liter) for 32 mo were placed in different concentrations of NaCl. Calli growth was inversely proportional to the concentration of NaCl in the medium, suggesting that stressed cells have only physiologically adjusted to high NaCl